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Minimal Polynomials of Linear Transformations

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DEDICATION

Dedicated to:

- My dear Parents.
- My sisters.
- My uncle Dr. Naseh F. Aruzari.
- My grand father.
- All my friends, special.

With love and Respect.

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ABSTRACT

We want look at the coordinate-free formulation of the idea of a diagonal matrix, which will be called a diagonalizable operator. There is a special polynomial, the minimal polynomial (generally not equal to the characteristic polynomial), which will tell us exactly when a linear operator is diagonalizable. The minimal polynomial will also give us information about nilpotent operators (those having a power equal to 0).

In this research we try to give some methods to specification the minimal polynomial. and some property of this polynomial. This project consists of two chapters.

The first chapter includes some basic definitions such as vector space, linear transformation, matrix of linear transformation, eigenvalue eigenvector, polynomial, some types of polynomials and some theorems.

The second chapter, starts with the definition of minimal polynomial. Then delineate some properties of minimal polynomial and some applications of minimal polynomial.

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Chapter 1

Polynomials And Linear Transformations

The objects of this chapter is general introductions. Whenever we need it to preparing a successful research about minimum polynomial the most important objects are vector space, linear transformation and the matrix of linear transformation and we have to know what is a polynomial and types of polynomial, so on how we need it to use in a linear transformation. here up on in this chapter we will define this important objects while we need it to polynomial and some methods for them.

1.1 Vector Spaces and Linear Transformations

In this section we introduce the objects we will be studying and give some of their basic properties. Also we try to know what is the vector space, and what we mean about a linear transformation, and give some applications of them.

The main objects of study in any course in linear algebra are linear functions.

Definition 1.1.1 *A vector space V over a field \mathbb{F} is a set V with a pair of operation $(u, v) \rightarrow u + v$ for $u, v \in V$ and $(c, u) \rightarrow cu$ for $c \in \mathbb{F}, v \in V$ satisfying the following axioms:*

1. $u + v \in V$ for any $u, v \in V$.
2. $u + v = v + u$ for any $u, v \in V$.
3. $(u + v) + w = u + (v + w)$ for any $u, v, w \in V$.
4. There is a $0 \in V$ such that $0 + v = v + 0 = v$ for any $v \in V$.
5. For any $v \in V$ there is a $-v \in V$ such that $v + (-v) = (-v) + v = 0$.
6. $cv \in V$ for any $c \in \mathbb{F}, v \in V$.
7. $c(u + v) = cu + cv$ for any $c \in \mathbb{F}, u, v \in V$.
8. $(c + d)u = cu + du$ for any $c, d \in \mathbb{F}, u \in V$.
9. $c(du) = (cd)u$ for any $c, d \in \mathbb{F}, u \in V$.
10. $1u = u$ for any $u \in V$.

[6]

Remark 1.1.2 *The elements of \mathbb{F} are called scalars and the elements of V are called vectors. The operation $(u, v) \mapsto u + v$ is called vector addition and the operation $(c, u) \mapsto cu$ is called scalar multiplication.*[6]

Definition 1.1.3 *Let V be a vector space. A non empty subset of V , $(\emptyset \neq U \subseteq V)$ is called a sub space of V if U itself is a vector space.*[5]

Theorem 1.1.4 *Let V be a vector space. Then U is a sub space iff*

$$i \ A + B \in U, \forall A, B \in U.$$

$$ii \ \alpha A \in U, \forall \alpha \in \mathbb{F}, \forall A \in U.$$

[5]

Definition 1.1.5 *A function $T : V \rightarrow W$ is linear transformations if V and W are vector spaces and*

$$T(A + B) = T(A) + T(B).$$

$$T(\alpha A) = \alpha T(A).$$

Or

$$T(\alpha A + \beta B) = \alpha T(A) + \beta T(B)$$

for all $A, B \in V$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{F}$. [5]

Lemma 1.1.6 *Let $T : V \rightarrow W$ be a linear transformation. Then $T(0) = 0$.*[6]

Definition 1.1.7 *Let V be a vector space. The identity linear transformation $I : V \rightarrow V$ is the linear transformation defined by*

$$I(v) = v \text{ for every } v \in V.$$

[6]

Theorem 1.1.8 *Let U, V , and W be vector spaces. Let $T : U \rightarrow V$ and $S : V \rightarrow W$ be linear transformations. Then the composition $S \circ T : U \rightarrow W$, defined by $(S \circ T)(u) = S(T(u))$, is a linear transformation.*

Proof:

$$(S \circ T)(cu) = S(T(cu)) = S(cT(u)) = cS(T(u)) = c(S \circ T)(u)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (S \circ T)(u_1 + u_2) &= S(T(u_1 + u_2)) = S(T(u_1) + T(u_2)) \\ &= S(T(u_1)) + S(T(u_2)) = (S \circ T)(u_1) + (S \circ T)(u_2). \end{aligned}$$

[6]

■

1.1.1 Basis and Dimension

In this subsection we develop the very important notion of a basis of a vector space. A basis B of the vector space V has two properties: B is linearly independent and B spans V . We begin by developing each of these two notions, which are important in their own right. We shall prove that any two bases of V have the same number of elements, which enables us to define the dimension of V as the number of elements in any basis of V .

Definition 1.1.9 Let $B = \{v_i\}$ be a subset of V . A vector $v \in V$ is a linear combination of the vectors in B if there is a set of scalars $\{c_i\}$, only finitely many of which are nonzero, such that

$$v = \sum c_i v_i.$$

[6]

Lemma 1.1.10 If we choose all $c_i = 0$ then we obtain

$$0 = \sum c_i v_i$$

This is the trivial linear combination of the vectors in B . Any other linear combination is nontrivial.[6]

Remark 1.1.11 In case $B = \{\}$, the only linear combination we have is the empty linear combination, whose value we consider to be $0 \in V$ and which we consider to be a trivial linear combination.[6]

Definition 1.1.12 Let $B = \{v_i\}$ be a subset of V . Then B is linearly independent if the only linear combination of elements of V that is equal to 0 is the trivial linear combination, i.e., if $0 = \sum c_i v_i$ implies $c_i = 0$ for every i . [6]

Definition 1.1.13 Let $B = \{v_i\}$ be a subset of V . Then $\text{Span}(B)$ is the subspace of V consisting of all linear combinations of elements of B ,

$$\text{Span}(B) = \left\{ \sum c_i v_i \mid c_i \in \mathbb{F} \right\}$$

If $\text{Span}(B) = V$ then B is a spanning set for V (or equivalently, B spans V). [6]

Definition 1.1.14 A subset B of a vector space V is called a base of V if

i B is a linear independent

ii B spans V .

[5]

Definition 1.1.15 Let X be a subset of vector space V then a sub space W of V is said to be generated by X if

i $X \subseteq W$

ii \forall subspace \bar{W} of V such that $X \subseteq \bar{W} \rightarrow W \subseteq \bar{W}$

Lemma 1.1.16 *Let $B = \{v_1, \dots, v_m\}$ span V . Any subset C of V containing more than m vectors is linearly dependent.*

Proof: Let $C = \{w_1, \dots, w_n\}$ with $n > m$. (If C is infinite consider a finite subset containing $n > m$ elements.) For each $i = 1, \dots, n$

$$w_i = \sum_{j=1}^m a_{ji} v_j$$

we show that

$$0 = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i w_i$$

has a nontrivial solution (i.e., a solution with not all $c_i = 0$). We have

$$0 = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i w_i = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i \left(\sum_{j=1}^m a_{ji} v_j \right) = \sum_{j=1}^m \left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ji} c_i \right) v_j$$

and this will be true if

$$0 = \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ji} c_i \quad \text{for each } j = 1, \dots, m.$$

This is a system of m equations in the n unknowns c_1, \dots, c_n and so has a nontrivial solution. [6] ■

Theorem 1.1.17 *Let V be a vector space. Then any two bases of V have the same number of elements.*

Proof: Let V have bases B and C . If both B and C are infinite, we are done. Assume not. Let B have m elements and C have n elements. Since B and C are bases, both B and C span V and both B and C are linearly independent. Applying Lemma 1.1.16 we see that $m \leq n$. Interchanging B and C we see that $n \leq m$. Hence $m = n$. [6] ■

Given this theorem we may make the following very important definition.

Definition 1.1.18 *Let V be a vector space. The dimension of V , $\dim(V)$, is the number of vectors in any basis of V , $\dim(V) \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\} \cup \{\infty\}$. [6]*

Lemma 1.1.19 *The vector space $V = \{0\}$ has basis $\{0\}$ and hence dimension 0. [6]*

Lemma 1.1.20 *i* A linear transformation $T : V \rightarrow W$ is specified by its values on any basis of V .

ii If $\{v_i\}$ is a basis of V and $\{w_i\}$ is an arbitrary set of vectors in W , then there is a unique linear transformation $T : V \rightarrow W$ with $T(v_i) = w_i$ for each i .

Proof:

- i Let $B = \{v_1, v_2, \dots\}$ be a basis of V and suppose that $T : V \rightarrow W$ and $T'' : V \rightarrow W$ are two linear transformations that agree on each v_i . Let $v \in V$ be arbitrary. We may write $v = \sum c_i v_i$, and then

$$T(v) = T\left(\sum c_i v_i\right) = \sum c_i T(v_i) = \sum c_i T''(v_i) = T''\left(\sum c_i v_i\right).$$

- ii Let $\{w_1, w_2, \dots\}$ be an arbitrary set of vectors in W , and define T as follows: For any $v \in V$, write $v = \sum c_i v_i$ and let

$$T(v) = \sum c_i T(v_i) = \sum c_i w_i$$

Since the expression for v is unique, this gives a well-defined function $T : V \rightarrow W$ with $T(v_i) = w_i$ for each i . It is routine to check that T is a linear transformation. Then T is unique by part (i).

[6] ■

While we will be considering both finite-dimensional and infinite-dimensional vector spaces, we adopt the convention that when we write (Let V be an n -dimensional vector space) or (Let V be a vector space of dimension n) we always mean that V is finite-dimensional, so that n is a nonnegative integer.

1.1.2 Indomorphism of Linear Transformation

Given a vectors space V over a field \mathbb{F} , we can define an endomorphism on V as a linear map from V to V . It may come as no surprise that the set of all endomorphisms on V , $End(V)$, forms a vector space, if we define scalar multiplication in the canonical way. If V has dimension n , then $End(V)$ has dimension n^2 (which can easily be seen by noticing the correspondence between $End(V)$ and the set of all $n \times n$ matrices). We shall now define a new algebraic structure, an algebra, and show that $End(V)$ is an algebra.

Definition 1.1.21 *An algebra is a vector space V with a bilinear product*

$$V \times V \rightarrow V$$

$$(v, w) \rightarrow vw$$

that distributes over vector addition

$$u(v + w) = uv + uw$$

and

$$(v + w)u = vu + wu$$

and satisfies $v(aw) = a(vw) = (av)w$ for all $a \in \mathbb{F}$. [2]

As the reader may notice, the definition of an algebra is similar to that of a ring. In fact, every algebra forms a ring. Rather than referring to this new operator as the bilinear product, we will simply refer to it as multiplication, although this is not to be confused with scalar multiplication.

We shall now show that $End(V)$ is, in fact, an algebra. For $T, R \in End(V)$, we define multiplication via

$$TR = T \circ R.$$

Clearly, for every $v \in V$ and $R, S, T \in End(V)$, we can see

$$(R(S + T))(v) = R(S(v) + T(v)) = (RS)(v) + (RT)(v) = (RS + RT)(v),$$

and

$$((S + T)R)(v) = (S + T)R(v) = (SR)(v) + (TR)(v) = (SR + TR)(v),$$

due to the linearity of R, S , and T . Then, for $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}$, again due to the linearity of each element, we can see that $R(\alpha T) = \alpha(RT) = (\alpha R)T$. Therefore, as we have already claimed $End(V)$ is a vector space, we can see that $End(V)$ is also an algebra.

Now that we have defined multiplication for endomorphisms, we can combine the theory of endomorphisms and polynomials. If we let $p(x)$ be a polynomial in $\mathbb{F}[x]$ and T be an endomorphism, then we can see that $p(T)$ is again an endomorphism, owing to $End(V)$ being an algebra. That is, for $v, w \in V$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}$,

$$p(T)(v + w) = p(T)(v) + p(T)(w),$$

and

$$p(T)(\alpha v) = \alpha p(T)(v).$$

We have now constructed the tools necessary to study minimum polynomials of linear transformations.

1.2 Matrices of Linear Transformation

Let V and W be vector spaces of finite dimensions n and m respectively with bases $B = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ and $C = \{w_1, \dots, w_m\}$ and let $T : V \rightarrow W$ is a linear transformation. Then we have isomorphisms $S : V \rightarrow F^n$ given by $S(v) = S[v]_B$ and $U : W \rightarrow F^m$ given by $U(w) = U[w]_C$, and we may form the composition $U \circ T \circ S^{-1} : F^n \rightarrow F^m$. Since this is a linear transformation, it is given by multiplication by a unique matrix. We are thus led to the following definition.

Definition 1.2.1 *Let V and W be two finite dimensional vector spaces over a field \mathbb{F} with $\dim V = n$ and $\dim W = m$ and let $\{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\}$ and $\{B_1, B_2, \dots, B_m\}$ be the ordered bases of V and W , respectively. If $T : V \rightarrow W$ is a linear transformation such that $T(A_j) = \sum_{i=1}^m a_{ij} B_i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ where $a_{ij} \in \mathbb{F}$, for all i and j . Then the matrix*

$$(a_{ij})_{m \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \cdots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix}_{m \times n}$$

is called the matrix of T relative to the ordered basis $\{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\}$ and $\{B_1, B_2, \dots, B_m\}$. [5]

It is clear that $T(A_j) \in W$, for all $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Since $\{B_1, B_2, \dots, B_m\}$ is a basis for W , so each $T(A_j)$ can be written as a linear combination of the vectors B_1, B_2, \dots, B_m . in a unique way That is,

$$\begin{aligned} T(A_1) &= a_{11}B_1 + a_{21}B_2 + \dots + a_{m1}B_m \\ T(A_2) &= a_{12}B_1 + a_{22}B_2 + \dots + a_{m2}B_m \\ &\vdots \\ T(A_n) &= a_{1n}B_1 + a_{2n}B_2 + \dots + a_{mn}B_m. \end{aligned}$$

Hence we get

$$\begin{bmatrix} T(A_1) \\ T(A_2) \\ \vdots \\ T(A_n) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} B_1 \\ B_2 \\ \vdots \\ B_m \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then $\begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix}^t = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix}$ is the matrix of T relative to the ordered bases $\{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\}$ and $\{B_1, B_2, \dots, B_m\}$.

Example 1.2.2 Let $T : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$, be the linear transformation defined by,

$$T(x, y, z) = (x + 2z, y - x, z + y), \text{ for all } (x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3.$$

Find the matrix of T relative to the standard basis $\{E_1^3, E_2^3, E_3^3\}$ of \mathbb{R}^3 used twice.

Solution: Now we have

$$\begin{aligned} T(E_1^3) &= T(1, 0, 0) = (1, -1, 0) = 1E_1^3 - 1E_2^3 + 0E_3^3. \\ T(E_2^3) &= T(0, 1, 0) = (0, 1, 1) = 0E_1^3 + 1E_2^3 + 1E_3^3. \\ T(E_3^3) &= T(0, 0, 1) = (2, 0, 0) = 2E_1^3 + 0E_2^3 + 0E_3^3. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the matrix of T relative to the standard basis $\{E_1^3, E_2^3, E_3^3\}$ is $\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 2 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$. [5]

Example 1.2.3 Let $S : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ be the linear transformation whose matrix relative to the

standard basis $\{E_1^3, E_2^3, E_3^3\}$ of \mathbb{R}^3 is $\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$. Find $S(x, y, z)$.

Solution: We have

$$\begin{aligned} S(E_1^3) &= S(1, 0, 0) = 2E_1^3 + 1E_2^3 - 1E_3^3 = (2, 1, -1). \\ S(E_2^3) &= S(0, 1, 0) = 0E_1^3 + 1E_2^3 + 1E_3^3 = (0, 1, 1). \\ S(E_3^3) &= S(0, 0, 1) = -1E_1^3 + 0E_2^3 + 1E_3^3 = (-1, 0, 1). \end{aligned}$$

Now, if $(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} S(x, y, z) &= S(x(1, 0, 0) + y(0, 1, 0) + z(0, 0, 1)) \\ &= xS(1, 0, 0) + yS(0, 1, 0) + zS(0, 0, 1) \\ &= x(2, 1, -1) + y(0, 1, 1) + z(-1, 0, 1) \\ &= (2x - z, x + y, -x + y + z), \end{aligned}$$

which is the general form of S . [5]

1.3 Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors

In this section we begin our analysis of the structure of a linear transformation $T : V \rightarrow V$, where V is a finite-dimensional \mathbb{F} -vector space.

We have arranged our exposition in order to bring some of the most important concepts to the fore first. Thus we begin with the notions of eigenvalues and eigenvectors, and we introduce the characteristic and minimum polynomials of a linear transformation early in this section as well. In this way we can get to some of the most important structural results, including results on diagonalizability, as quickly as possible.

Definition 1.3.1 *The linear transformation T is called diagonalizable if there exists a basis for V with respect to which the matrix for T is a diagonal matrix.*[1]

Let's look at what it means for the matrix of T to be diagonal. Recall that we get the matrix by choosing a basis $\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$, and then entering the coordinates of $T(u_1)$ as the first column, the coordinates of $T(u_2)$ as the second column, etc. The matrix is diagonal, with entries $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$ if and only if the chosen basis has the property that $T(u_i) = \alpha_i u_i$, for $1 \leq i \leq n$. This leads to the definition of an "eigenvalue" and its corresponding "eigenvectors".

Definition 1.3.2 *A scalar $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}$ is called an eigenvalue of T if there exists a nonzero vector $v \in V$ such that*

$$T(v) = \alpha v.$$

In this case, v is called an eigenvector of T belonging to the eigenvalue α .[1]

As noted above, the significance of this definition is that there is a diagonal matrix that represents T if and only if there exists a basis for V that consists of eigenvectors of T . Note that the terms *characteristic value* and *eigenvalue* are used synonymously, as are the terms *characteristic vector* and *eigenvector*.

If v_1 and v_2 are eigenvectors belonging to the eigenvalue α of T , then so is any nonzero vector $a_1 v_1 + a_2 v_2$, since

$$T(a_1 v_1 + a_2 v_2) = a_1 T(v_1) + a_2 T(v_2) = a_1 \alpha v_1 + a_2 \alpha v_2 = \alpha (a_1 v_1 + a_2 v_2).$$

For each of T , the set of eigenvectors that belong to it, together with the zero vector, forms a subspace.

Definition 1.3.3 *For any eigenvalue α of T , any $v \in V$ is called an eigenvector of T belonging to α if $T(v) = \alpha v$, the set of all eigenvectors of T belonging to an eigenvalue α is called the eigen space belonging to α .*[7]

Let A be an $n \times n$ matrix over \mathbb{F} and $T : V \rightarrow V$ be a linear transformation such that A is the matrix of T relative to some ordered basis $B = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$ of V . Then by an eigenvalue of A we mean an eigenvalue of T , and an n -tuple $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n)$ in $\mathbb{F}^{(n)}$ is called an eigenvector of A if $\alpha_1 v_1 + \alpha_2 v_2 + \dots + \alpha_n v_n$ is an eigenvector of T .

Eigenvectors and eigenvalues are also called characteristic vectors and characteristic values (or roots) respectively.

Theorem 1.3.4 *Let $(T \neq 0) \in A(V)$ and let v be an eigen vector of T and $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}$ such that $T(v) = \alpha v$. Then for any $f(x) \in \mathbb{F}[x]$, v is an eigen vector of $f(T)$ and $[f(T)](v) = f(\alpha)v$.*

Proof: Now $T(v) = \alpha v \Rightarrow T^2(v) = T[T(v)] = T(\alpha v) = \alpha T(v) = \alpha(\alpha v) = \alpha^2 v$. $T^3(v) = T[T^2(v)] = T(\alpha^2 v) = \alpha^2 T(v) = \alpha^2(\alpha v) = \alpha^3 v$. In general for any positive integer k , $T^k(v) = \alpha^k(v)$. Then for any $f(x) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x + \dots + \beta_m x^m \in \mathbb{F}[x]$, $[f(T)](v) = (\beta_0 I + \beta_1 T + \dots + \beta_m T^m)(v) = \beta_0 v + \beta_1(T(v)) + \beta_2[T^2(v)] + \dots + \beta_m[T^m(v)] = \beta_0 v + \beta_1(\alpha v) + \beta_2(\alpha^2 v) + \dots + \beta_m(\alpha^m v) = (\beta_0 + \beta_1 \alpha + \beta_2 \alpha^2 + \dots + \beta_m \alpha^m)(v) = f(\alpha)(v)$. [7] ■

Let's translate diagonalizability into the language of eigenvectors rather than matrices.

Theorem 1.3.5 *The linear operator $A : V \rightarrow V$ is diagonalizable if and only if there is a basis of eigenvectors for A in V .*

Proof: Suppose there is a basis $B = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ of V in which $[A]_B$ is diagonal:

$$[A]_B = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & a_2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & a_n \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $Ae_i = a_i e_i$ for all i , so each e_i is an eigenvector for A . Conversely, if V has a basis $\{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ of eigenvectors of A , with $Av_i = \lambda_i v_i$ for $\lambda_i \in \mathbb{F}$, then in this basis the matrix representation of A is $diag(\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n)$. [4] ■

A basis of eigenvectors for an operator is called an *eigenbasis*.

1.4 Polynomial

The focus of this reaserch is on the minimum polynomial of a linear transformation, and the various consequences which arise when studying the minimum polynomial. However, before we begin, we shall review basic information about polynomials in general. While typical first courses in linear algebra focus on vectors spaces with scalars from the field \mathbb{C} , we shall focus on vector spaces with scalars from any field \mathbb{F} . Thus, in the course of this paper, the polynomials in question will always be elements of $\mathbb{F}[x]$. Recall that one of the primary differences between studying vector spaces over \mathbb{C} and vector spaces over \mathbb{F} comes from irreducible factors, and consequences of the field \mathbb{C} being algebraically closed. Hence, any polynomial in $\mathbb{C}[x]$ can be factored into linear factors, and so irreducible elements in $\mathbb{C}[x]$ are trivial. This, of course, is not true in the general $\mathbb{F}[x]$ case. We shall review some basic information about polynomials from $\mathbb{F}[x]$, but we omit the proofs of theorems as the material should be review.

Definition 1.4.1 *A polynomial $f(x) \in \mathbb{F}[x]$, given by $f(x) = \alpha_n x^n + \alpha_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + \alpha_1 x + \alpha_0$, is monic if $\alpha_n = 1$. [2]*

Theorem 1.4.2 (Division Theorem) *Given $f(x), g(x) \in \mathbb{F}[x]$, with $g(x)$ monic, there exist unique polynomials $q(x)$ and $r(x)$, with $\deg r(x) < \deg g(x)$, such that $f(x) = q(x)g(x) + r(x)$. [2]*

Example 1.4.3 *Let $f(x) = 3x^2 - 4x + 7$, and $g(x) = x - 1$ then applying the Division theorem of $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ we get*

$$\underbrace{3x^2 - 4x + 7}_{f(x)} = \underbrace{(3x - 1)}_{q(x)} \underbrace{(x - 1)}_{g(x)} + \underbrace{6}_{r(x)}$$

For the special case we can see that if $g(x) = x - a$, we get the remainder is equal to $f(a)$. fo example see example 1.4.3. [8]

1.4.1 Irreducible Polynomial

Definition 1.4.4 (Irreducible or prime polynomial) A non-constant polynomial $f(x) \in \mathbb{F}[x]$ is irreducible if there are no $g(x), h(x) \in \mathbb{F}[x]$, where the degrees of $g(x)$ and $h(x)$ are both less than the degree of $f(x)$, such that $f(x) = g(x)h(x)$. [3]

Now the natural question is how we can determine the polynomial is irreducible or not?
or

Given a polynomial over a field, what are the methods to see it is irreducible? Only two comes to my mind now. First is Eisenstein criterion. Another is that if a polynomial is irreducible mod p then it is irreducible. Are there any others?

The answer for this question is there are no rules to finding the irreducible(prime) polynomial, all we have for this polynomial is the theorem and some testing:

Test1. (Rabin's test for irreducibility)

Let $f(x)$ be a polynomial of degree n over \mathbb{F}_p . Then f is irreducible over \mathbb{F}_p if and only if

- $f(x)$ divides $x^{p^n} - x$, and
- $\gcd(f(x), x^{p^{n/q}} - x) = 1$ for each prime divisor q of n . [9]

Test2. (Test for Degrees 2 and 3)

Let \mathbb{F} be a field, $f(x) \in \mathbb{F}[x]$, and $\deg f(x) = 2$ or 3 . **Then** $f(x)$ is reducible over \mathbb{F} **if and only if** $f(x)$ has a zero in \mathbb{F} .

Test3. (\mathbb{Q} implies \mathbb{Z})

Let $f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. **If** $f(x)$ is reducible over \mathbb{Q} , **then** it is also reducible over \mathbb{Z} .

Test4. Let p be a prime number and $f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$ with $\deg f(x) \geq 1$. Let $\bar{f}(x) \in \mathbb{Z}_p[x]$ be obtained from $f(x)$ by reducing all the coefficients modulo p . **If** $\bar{f}(x)$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Z}_p and $\deg \bar{f}(x) = \deg f(x)$, **then** $f(x)$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

[Test5.] Eisensteins Criterion)

Let $f(x) = a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \cdots + a_1 x + a_0 \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. **If** there is a prime p such that $p | a_{n-1}, p | a_{n-2}, \cdots, p | a_0$, **but** $p \nmid a_n$ and $p^2 \nmid a_0$, **then** $f(x)$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

Theorem 1.4.5 The eigenvalues of T are the zeros (roots) of its characteristic polynomial.

Definition 1.4.6 Let $f(x) = a_m x^m + \cdots + a_1 x + a_0$ be a polynomial in $\mathbb{F}[x]$. Then $f(T)$ denotes the linear transformation

$$f(T) = a_m T^m + \cdots + a_1 T + a_0 I : V \rightarrow V,$$

where I is the identity on V . Similarly, if A is an $n \times n$ matrix, then $f(A)$ denotes the $n \times n$ matrix

$$f(A) = a_m A^m + \cdots + a_1 A + a_0 I,$$

where I is the $n \times n$ identity matrix.

1.4.2 T-annihilator Polynomial

Theorem 1.4.7 (Annihilator Polynomial) *Let V be an n -dimensional vector space, T an endomorphism of V , and $v \in V$ a non-zero vector. Then there is a unique monic polynomial of minimum degree, $m_{T,v}(x)$ such that $m_{T,v}(T)(v) = 0$. This polynomial has degree at most n .*

Proof: Consider the set $A = \{v, T(v), \dots, T^n(v)\}$. Then A is a set of $n + 1$ vectors in an n -dimensional vector space, and must be linearly dependent. Therefore, there exist scalars a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n , not all zero, such that

$$a_n T^n(v) + a_{n-1} T^{n-1}(v) + \dots + a_0 v = 0.$$

We can express this linear combination of vectors as a polynomial $p(x)$ evaluated at $T(v)$, where $p(x) = a_n x^n + \dots + a_1 x + a_0$ is such a polynomial. Let us denote the coefficient on the leading term, that is, the coefficient on the highest power term with a nonzero coefficient. If we define $m_{T,v}(x) = b_n x^n + b_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + b_0$, where $b_i = \frac{a_i}{a_n}$, then $m_{T,v}$ is a monic polynomial. Because $m, T, v(T)(v) = 1$ as $p(T)(v) = 0$, then $m_{T,v}(x)$ is satisfied by $T(v)$, and therefore there exists a monic polynomial $m_{T,v}(x)$ with degree at most n such that $m_{T,v}(T)(v) = 0$. Because n is finite, then there must exist a monic polynomial of minimal degree that $T(v)$ satisfies. To show uniqueness, let m and m'' be two monic polynomials of minimum degree that $T(v)$ satisfies. Then clearly, $T(v)$ must satisfy $(m - m'')$. However, because m and m'' are both monic, $\deg(m - m'') < \deg m$, which contradicts the minimality of $\deg m$. Thus, $m_{T,v}(x)$ is unique. [2] ■

Definition 1.4.8 *The polynomial from the previous theorem, $m_{T,v}(x)$, is the T -annihilator polynomial of v . [2]*

Example 1.4.9 *Let V have basis $\{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ and define T by $T(v_1) = 0$ and $T(v_i) = v_{i-1}$ for $i > 1$. Then $m_{T,v_k}(x) = x^k$ for $k = 1, \dots, n$. This shows that $m_{T,v}(x)$ can have any degree between 1 and n . [6]*

1.4.3 Characteristic polynomial

Definition 1.4.10 *Let A be a matrix of T with respect to some basis of V . Then the polynomial $f(x) = D(xI - A)$ is called the characteristic polynomial of T . [3]*

Theorem 1.4.11 *Let A and B be similar matrices. Then the characteristic polynomials of A and B , $c_A(x)$ and $c_B(x)$, are equal.*

Proof: First, let $B = P^{-1}AP$. Then we can see that for any $x \in \mathbb{F}$,

$$\begin{aligned} xI - B &= xP^{-1}P - P^{-1}AP \\ &= P^{-1}xP - P^{-1}AP \\ &= P^{-1}(xI - A)P. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \det(xI - B) &= \det(P^{-1}(xI - A)P) \\
 &= \det(P^{-1}) \det(xI - A) \det(P) \\
 &= \det(P)^{-1} \det(xI - A) \det(P) \\
 &= \det(xI - A).
 \end{aligned}$$

[2] ■

1.5 Inverse of linear Transformations

Definition 1.5.1 $T \in A(V)$ is called right (left) invertible if there exists $S \in A(V)$ such that $TS = I$ ($ST = I$) where I is the identity transformation on V . [7]

Note 1.5.2 S is called a right (left) inverse of T . [7]

Definition 1.5.3 $T \in A(V)$ is called invertible or regular if T is both right and left invertible. [7]

Lemma 1.5.4 if $T \in A(V)$ is regular then there exists $S \in A(V)$ such that $ST = TS = I$.

Proof: Since T is both right and left invertible there exist $S', S'' \in A(V)$ such that $TS' = I$ and $S''T = I$. Now $S' = IS' = (S''T)S' = S''(TS') = S''I = S''$. putting $S = S' = S''$ we get that $TS = ST = I$. [7] ■

Definition 1.5.5 An invertible linear transformation $T : V \rightarrow W$ is called an isomorphism. Two vector spaces V and W are isomorphic if there is an isomorphism $T : V \rightarrow W$. [6]

Chapter 2

The Minimal Polynomial and Some Applications

There is a special polynomial, the minimal polynomial (generally not equal to the characteristic polynomial), which will tell us exactly when a linear operator is diagonalizable. The minimal polynomial will also give us information about nilpotent operators (those having a power equal to 0).

2.1 Minimal Polynomial

Definition 2.1.1 Let $(T \neq 0) \in A(V)$. The monic polynomial $m(x) = x^k - \alpha_1 x^{k-1} - \dots - \alpha_k$ over \mathbb{F} is called minimal polynomial of T if

$$i \ m(T) = T^k - \alpha_1 T^{k-1} - \alpha_2 T^{k-2} - \dots - \alpha_k I = 0$$

$$ii \ \text{for any } g(x) \in \mathbb{F}[x], g(T) = 0$$

if and only if $m(x)$ divides $g(x)$. [7]

Theorem 2.1.2 Let V be a vector space of dimension n . Then there is a unique monic polynomial $m_T(x)$ of lowest degree with $m_T(T)(v) = 0$ for every $v \in V$. This polynomial has degree at most n^2 .

Proof: Choose a basis $B = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ of V . For each $v_k \in B$ we have its T -annihilator $p_k(x) = m_{T, v_k}(x)$. Let $q(x)$ be the least common multiple of $p_1(x), \dots, p_n(x)$. Since $p_k(x)$ divides $q(x)$ for each k , $q(T)(v_k) = 0$. Hence $q(T)(v) = 0$ for every $v \in V$ by Lemma 1.1.20. If $r(x)$ is any polynomial with $r(x)$ not divisible by $p_k(x)$ for some k , then for that value of k we have $r(T)(v_k) \neq 0$. Thus $m_T(x) = q(x)$ is the desired polynomial. $m_T(x)$ divides the product $p_1(x)p_2(x) \cdots p_n(x)$, of degree n^2 , so $m_T(x)$ has degree at most n^2 . [6] ■

Lemma 2.1.3 Let V be a vector space and let $T : V \rightarrow V$ be a linear transformation. Let $v_1, \dots, v_k \in V$ with T -annihilators $p_i(x) = m_{T, v_i}(x)$ for $i = 1, \dots, k$ and suppose that $p_1(x), \dots, p_k(x)$ are pairwise relatively prime. Let $v = v_1 + \dots + v_k$ have T -annihilator $p(x) = m_{T, v}(x)$. Then $p(x) = p_1(x) \cdots p_k(x)$. [6]

Theorem 2.1.4 Let V be a finite-dimensional vector space and let $T : V \rightarrow V$ be a linear transformation. Then there is a vector $v \in V$ such that the T -annihilator $m_{T, v}(x)$ of v is equal to the minimum polynomial $m_T(x)$ of T . [6]

Proof: Choose a basis $B = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ of V . As we have seen in Theorem 2.1.2, the minimum polynomial $m_T(x)$ is the least common multiple of the T -annihilators $m_{T,v_1}(x), \dots, m_{T,v_n}(x)$. Factor $m_T(x) = p_1(x)^{f_1} \cdots p_k(x)^{f_k}$ where $p_1(x), \dots, p_k(x)$ are distinct irreducible polynomials, and hence $p_1(x)^{f_1}, \dots, p_k(x)^{f_k}$ are pairwise relatively prime polynomials. For each i between 1 and k , $p_i(x)^{f_i}$ must appear as a factor of $m_{T,v_j}(x)$ for some j . Write $m_{T,v_j}(x) = p_i(x)^{f_i} q(x)$. Then the vector $u_i = q(T)(v_j)$ has T -annihilator $p_i(x)^{f_i}$. By Lemma 5.1.10, the vector $v = u_1 + \cdots + u_k$ has T -annihilator $p_1(x)^{f_1} \cdots p_k(x)^{f_k} = m_T(x)$. ■

Theorem 2.1.5 *Let $(T \neq 0) \in A(V)$ and $S \in A(V)$ be invertible. Then T and $S^{-1}TS$ have same minimal polynomials.*

Proof: Now for any $g(x) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 x + \cdots + \alpha_k x^k$ in $\mathbb{F}[x]$, $g(S^{-1}TS) = \alpha_0 I + \alpha_1 (S^{-1}TS) + \alpha_2 (S^{-1}TS)^2 + \cdots + \alpha_k (S^{-1}TS)^k$. However $(S^{-1}TS)^m = S^{-1}T^m S$ for all integers $m \geq 0$. Hence $g(S^{-1}TS) = \alpha_0 I + \alpha_1 S^{-1}TS + \alpha_2 S^{-1}T^2 S + \cdots + \alpha_k S^{-1}T^k S = S^{-1}(\alpha_0 I + \alpha_1 T + \alpha_2 T^2 + \cdots + \alpha_k T^k)S = S^{-1}g(T)S$. Hence $g(T) = 0 \Leftrightarrow g(S^{-1}TS) = 0$. So that if $m(x)$ and $m'(x)$ are the minimal polynomials of T and $S^{-1}TS$ respectively then $m(T) = 0, m'(T) = 0, m'(S^{-1}TS) = 0, m(S^{-1}TS) = 0$. The definition of minimal polynomial yields $m(x)|m'(x)$ and $m'(x)|m(x)$. Hence $m(x) = m'(x)$, since both are monic. This proves the result. ■

Theorem 2.1.6 (a) *The minimal polynomial of T exists and is unique.*

(b) *If $m(x)$ is the minimal polynomial of T and $f(x)$ is any polynomial with $f(T) = 0$, then $m(x)$ is a factor of $f(x)$.*

Proof: Let $m(x)$ be a monic polynomial of minimal degree such that $m(T) = 0$. Suppose that $f(x)$ is any polynomial with $f(T) = 0$. The division algorithm holds for polynomials with coefficients in the field \mathbb{F} , so it is possible to write $f(x) = q(x)m(x) + r(x)$, where either $r(x) = 0$ or $\deg(r(x)) < \deg(m(x))$. If $r(x)$ is nonzero, then we have $r(T) = f(T) - q(T)m(T) = 0$. We can divide $r(x)$ by its leading coefficient to obtain a monic polynomial satisfied by T , and then this contradicts the choice of $m(x)$ as a monic polynomial of minimal degree satisfied by T . We conclude that the remainder $r(x)$ is zero, so $f(x) = q(x)m(x)$ and $m(x)$ is thus a factor of $f(x)$. If $h(x)$ is another monic polynomial of minimal degree with $h(T) = 0$, then by the preceding paragraph $m(x)$ is a factor of $h(x)$, and $h(x)$ is a factor of $m(x)$. Since both are monic polynomials, this forces $h(x) = m(x)$, showing that the minimal polynomial is unique. ■

We will usually denote the minimal polynomial of A as $m_A(T)$.

Theorem 2.1.7 *Let $A : V \rightarrow V$ be linear. A polynomial $f(T) \in \mathbb{F}[T]$ satisfies $f(A) = 0$ if and only if $m_A(T)|f(T)$.*

Proof: Suppose $m_A(T)|f(T)$, so $f(T) = m_A(T)g(T)$. Since substitution of A for T gives a homomorphism $\mathbb{F}[T] \rightarrow \text{hom}_F(V, V)$, we have $f(A) = m_A(A)g(A) = 0 \cdot pg(A) = 0$. Conversely, suppose $f(A) = 0$. Using polynomial division in $\mathbb{F}[T]$, write $f(T) = m_A(T)q(T) + r(T)$ where $q(T), r(T) \in \mathbb{F}[T]$ and $r(T) = 0$ or $\deg r < \deg m_A$. Substituting A for T in the polynomials, we have

$$0 = m_A(A)q(A) + r(A) = r(A).$$

Since $r(T)$ vanishes at A and either $r(T) = 0$ or $r(T)$ has degree less than the degree of the minimal polynomial of A , it must be the case that $r(T) = 0$. Therefore $f(T) = m_A(T)q(T)$, so $m_A(T)|f(T)$. ■

Definition 2.1.8 We say that $m(x)$ is also the minimal polynomial of the matrix A .

Theorem 2.1.9 A linear transformation $T : V \rightarrow V$ is regular if and only if its minimal polynomial has non-zero constant term.

Proof: Let $m(x) = x^k - \alpha_1 x^{k-1} - \alpha_2 x^{k-2} - \dots - \alpha_k$ be the minimal polynomial of T . Then $T^k - \alpha_1 T^{k-1} - \alpha_2 T^{k-2} - \dots - \alpha_k I = 0$ yields $T(T^{k-1} - \alpha_1 T^{k-2} - \dots - \alpha_{k-1} I) = (T^{k-1} - \alpha_1 T^{k-2} - \dots - \alpha_{k-1} I)T = \alpha_k I \dots (*)$

Let T be a regular. If $\alpha_k = 0$, then as T^{-1} exists, $(*)$ implies that $T^{k-1} - \alpha_1 T^{k-2} - \dots - \alpha_{k-1} I = 0$.

This contradicts the fact that $\deg m(x) = k$ and T can not be a root of any non-zero polynomial over \mathbb{F} of degree $< k$. Hence $\alpha_k \neq 0$.

Conversely if $\alpha_k \neq 0$, then $(*)$ yields that $TT' = T'T = I$ where $T' = \alpha_k^{-1}(T^{k-1} - \alpha_1 T^{k-2} - \dots - \alpha_{k-1} I)$. Hence T is regular. \blacksquare

Corollary 2.1.10 If $T \in A(V)$ is regular then T^{-1} is a polynomial in T over \mathbb{F} .

Proof: if $x^k - \alpha_1 x^{k-1} - \alpha_2 x^{k-2} - \dots - \alpha_k$ is the minimal polynomial of T over \mathbb{F} then as we have seen in the proof of above theorem, $\alpha_k \neq 0$ and $T' = \alpha_k^{-1}(T^{k-1} - \alpha_1 T^{k-2} - \dots - \alpha_{k-1} I)$, a polynomial in T over \mathbb{F} . \blacksquare

Example 2.1.11 Consider $V = \mathbb{Q}^3$. Let (e_1, e_2, e_3) be its standard bases. Let $T \in A(V)$

have the corresponding matrix with respect to standard basis, given by $A = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$. Then

$A - 2I = 0$ where $I = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$. Hence $T - 2I = 0$. This shows that T is a root of the

monic polynomial $x - 2$. Since the minimal polynomial of T is a monic polynomial of least positive degree, of which T is a root, we get that $x - 2$ is the minimal polynomial of T .

Example 2.1.12 Consider linear transformation $T : \mathbb{Q}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}^3$ such that $T(e_1) = e_2, T(e_2) = e_3, T(e_3) = e_1$ where (e_1, e_2, e_3) is the standard basis of \mathbb{Q}^3 . The matrix of T with respect to

this basis is $A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. $A^2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. $A^3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$. So $T^3 - I = 0$. Hence

the minimal polynomial $m(x)$ of T divides $x^3 - 1$. So $\deg m(x) \leq 3$. If $\deg m(x) = 1$, then $m(x) = x - \alpha$ for some $\alpha \in \mathbb{Q}$ gives $A - \alpha I = O$, i.e., $A - \alpha I$ a diagonal matrix. This is a contradiction. Hence $\deg m(x) > 1$. If $\deg m(x) = 2$, then $m(x) = x^2 - \alpha x - \beta$ for some $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{Q}$.

Hence $A^2 - \alpha A - \beta I = 0$ implies that $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \alpha \\ \alpha & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha & 0 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \beta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \beta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \beta \end{pmatrix} =$

$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ i.e. $\begin{pmatrix} -\beta & 1 & -\alpha \\ -\beta & -\alpha & 1 \\ 1 & -\alpha & -\beta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. Hence $1 = 0$. This is absurd!. Hence $\deg m(x) > 2$. So as $m(x) | x^3 - 1$, we get $\deg m(x) = 3$ and $m(x) = x^3 - 1$. Thus $x^3 - 1$ is the minimal polynomial of T over \mathbb{Q} .

Definition 2.1.13 Let $f(x) = x^n + a_{n-1}x^{n-1} + \cdots + a_1x + a_0$ be a monic polynomial in $\mathbb{F}x$ of degree $n > 1$. Then the companion matrix $C(f(x))$ of $f(x)$ is the n -by- n matrix

$$C(f(x)) = \begin{bmatrix} -a_{n-1} & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ -a_{n-2} & 0 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -a_1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 1 \\ -a_0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

(The 1s are immediately above the diagonal.)

[6]

Theorem 2.1.14 Let $f(x) = x^n + a_{n-1}x^{n-1} + \cdots + a_0$ be a monic polynomial and let $A = C(f(x))$ be its companion matrix. Let $V = \mathbb{F}^n$ and let $T = T_A$ be an endomorphism of V defined by $T(v) = Av$. Let $v = e_n$ be the n th standard basis vector. Then the subspace W of V defined by $W = \{g(T)(v) | g(x) \in \mathbb{F}[x]\}$ is V . Furthermore, $m_T(x) = m_{T,v}(x) = f(x)$. [6]

Proof: We see that $T(e_n) = e_{n-1}$, $T^2(e_n) = e_{n-2}$, and in general $T^k(e_n) = e_{n-k}$ for $k \leq n-1$. Thus, the subspace W of V contains the subspace spanned by $\{T^{n-1}(v), \dots, T(v), v\} = \{e_1, \dots, e_{n-1}, e_n\}$, the standard basis vectors of V , which is all of V . We also see that this set is linearly independent, and hence there is no nonzero polynomial $p(x)$ with degree less than or equal to $n-1$ with $p(T)(v) = 0$. From

$$\begin{aligned} T^n(v) &= T(e_1) = -a_{n-1}e_1 - a_{n-2}e_2 \cdots - a_0e_n \\ &= -a_{n-1}T^{n-1}(v) - a_{n-2}T^{n-2}(v) \cdots - a_1T(v) - a_0v \end{aligned}$$

we see that

$$0 = a_nT^n(v) + \cdots + a_1T(v) + a_0v,$$

which is to say $f(T)(v) = 0$. Therefore, $m_{T,v}(x) = f(x)$.

On the one hand, $m_{T,v}(x)$ divides $m_T(x)$, an obvious consequence of both polynomials being satisfied by $T(v)$. On the other hand, since every $w \in V$ is $w = g(T)(v)$ for some polynomial $g(x)$,

$$\begin{aligned} m_{T,v}(T)(w) &= m_{T,v}(T)g(T)(v) \\ &= g(T)m_{T,v}(T)(v) \\ &= g(T)(0) \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

for every $w \in V$. Thus, $m_T(x)$ divides $m_{T,v}(x)$. Therefore, we can see that

$$m_T(x) = m_{T,v}(x) = f(x).$$

■

2.2 The Relationship Between The Characteristic and Minimum Polynomials

Cayley Hamilton Theorem: Let A be an $n \times n$ matrix of real elements. The determinantal equation defining its eigenvalues is

$$\det(AI) = 0$$

where I is the $n \times n$ identity matrix. This equation in terms of a determinant generates a polynomial equation $p(\lambda) = 0$ where $p(\lambda)$ is called the characteristic polynomial of the matrix. The Cayley-Hamilton Theorem is that if A is substituted for λ in the characteristic polynomial the result is a matrix of zeros.

Proof: The characteristic polynomial equation is equivalent to the determinantal equation

$$\det(A - \lambda I) = 0$$

The expression λI is the diagonal matrix Λ so the determinantal equation is really

$$\det(A - \Lambda) = 0$$

If A is substituted for Λ in this equation the result is

$$\det(A - A) = \det(O) = 0$$

where O is a matrix of zeros. Certainly A satisfies the determinantal equation. [10] ■

Cayley Hamilton Theorem states that if A is an $n \times n$ matrix over the field \mathbb{F} then $p(A) = 0$.

Example 2.2.1 Let A be the matrix $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ 3 & 4 \end{pmatrix}$ Then the matrix $A\lambda I$ is $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ 3 & 4 \end{pmatrix}$ The determinant of $(A - \lambda I)$ is then $(1 - \lambda)(4 - \lambda) - 2 * 3$ which reduces to $4 - 5\lambda + \lambda^2 - 6$ and further to $-2 - 5\lambda + \lambda^2$ This is the characteristic polynomial of the matrix A . The solutions to the polynomial equation $-2 - 5\lambda + \lambda^2 = 0$ are the eigenvalues of the matrix A .

Consider now what results when λ is replaced with A and -2 is replaced with $-2I$. A^2 is the matrix $\begin{pmatrix} 7 & 10 \\ 15 & 22 \end{pmatrix}$ Therefore $-2I - 5A + A^2$ is $\begin{pmatrix} -2 - 5 * 1 + 7 & 0 - 5 * 2 + 10 \\ 0 - 5 - 3 + 15 & -2 - 5 * 4 + 22 \end{pmatrix}$ which evaluates to $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ Thus, almost mystically, A satisfies its own eigenvalue value equation. [10]

Theorem 2.2.2 Let V be a finite-dimensional vector space and T an endomorphism of V . Let $m_T(x)$ and $c_T(x)$ be the minimum polynomial and characteristic polynomial of T , respectively. Then $m_T(x)$ divides $c_T(x)$. [2]

Proof: From the Cayley-Hamilton theorem, we know that $c_T(T) = 0$. Thus, by the division theorem, there exist unique polynomials $q(x)$ and $r(x)$ such that

$$c_T(x) = q(x)m_T(x) + r(x),$$

where $\deg r(x) < \deg m_T(x)$. However, we can clearly see that $c_T(T) = 0$ implies $r(T) = 0$. Because $r(x)$ has degree strictly less than $m_T(x)$, this violates the minimality of the degree of $m_T(x)$ unless $r(x) = 0$. Thus, $m_T(x)$ divides $c_T(x)$. ■

Theorem 2.2.3 *Let V be an n dimensional vector space and let $T : V \rightarrow V$ be a linear transformation. Then V is T -generated by a single element if and only if $m_T(x)$ is a polynomial of degree n , or, equivalently, if and only if $m_T(x) = c_T(x)$. [6]*

Proof: For $w \in V$, let W be the subspace of V T -generated by w . Then the dimension of W is equal to the degree of $m_{T,w}(x)$, and $m_{T,w}(x)$ divides $m_T(x)$. Thus if $m_T(x)$ has degree less than n , W has dimension less than n and so $W \subset V$. By Theorem 2.1.4, there is a vector $v_0 \in V$ with $m_{T,v_0}(x) = m_T(x)$. Thus if $m_T(x)$ has degree n , the subspace V_0 of V generated by v_0 has dimension n and so $V_0 = V$. Since $m_T(x)$ and $c_T(x)$ are both monic polynomials, and $m_T(x)$ divides $c_T(x)$ by Theorem 2.2.2, then $m_T(x) = c_T(x)$ if and only if they have the same degree. But $c_T(x)$ has degree n . ■

So far, our examples have shown that $m_T(x) = c_T(x)$. This is not true in general. Consider

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 3 & 3 \\ 4 & 4 & 4 \\ 5 & 5 & 5 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $c_T(x) = x^2(x - 12)$. We will see that this implies $m_T(x) = x(x - 12)$, and $m_T(x) \neq c_T(x)$. [3]

Theorem 2.2.4 *Every eigenvalue of $T \in A(V)$ is a root of the minimum polynomial of T .*

Proof: Let $m(x)$ be the minimum polynomial of T . let $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}$ be an eigen value of T . Then for some non-zero $v \in V, T(v) = \alpha v$. By lemma 1.3, $[f(T)](v) = f(\alpha)v$ for every $f(x) \in \mathbb{F}[x]$. In particular $[m(T)](v) = m(\alpha)v$. This yields that $m(\alpha)v = 0$, since $m(T) = 0$. Hence $m(\alpha) = 0$ as $v \neq 0$. Thus α is a root of the minimal polynomial of T . ■

Example 2.2.5 *Let's do a larger example: $c_T(x) = (x^2 + 2)2(x^4 + 1)$.*

Then

$$C(c_T(x)) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -4 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -5 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$m_T(x) = c_T(x)$ since it is a Companion matrix.

Now the natural question is (Why are minimal polynomials important?)

The answer is clear since minimal polynomials carry more information than characteristic polynomials; not only do they give you the eigenvalues (like the characteristic polynomials do), they also give you the size of the largest Jordan block associated to any given eigenvalue in the Jordan canonical form of the linear transformation, the size of the largest companion block associated to any given irreducible factor in the rational canonical form, a necessary and sufficient condition for diagonalizability (T is diagonalizable if and only if the minimal polynomial of T splits and has no repeated roots), and more besides.

2.3 Problems

i Find the minimal polynomials of each of the following matrices over \mathbb{Q} and if any of them is non singular find also its inverse:

(a) $\begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ -1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$

(b) $\begin{pmatrix} 3 & -3 \\ -2 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$

(c) $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & -2 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$

(d) $\begin{pmatrix} 2 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$

ii Show that the minimal polynomial of $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$ is $x^4 - 3x^3 + x - 1 = 0$,

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